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Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

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CreaSTEAM Project

Lack of diversity, especially gender inequality and social background are some global problems in different sectors but especially latent in the context of the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering (and the recently added concept of Arts), and Mathematics (STEAM), from primary school to university level and, therefore, labor market.

CreaSTEAM project aims to provide an actualized map of the resources focused on the reduction of the diversity gap using STEAM approaches, and how to select from these resources better solutions to create a framework to implement STEAM-Labs into secondary schools. The STEAM-Labs, as a main innovation of the project, merge the solutions

that we can find in FAB-Labs, MEDIA-Labs, and USER-Labs, and our approach is focused on the creation of good practices in these spaces in order to promote diversity in STEAM, where diversity also covers gender equity, and social inclusion for promotion of STEAM vocations.

Partners

- Ramon Llull University-La Salle, Spain
- University of Salamanca, Spain
- FIDAE, Italy
- Bursa MEM, Turkey
- Sadettin Türkün Ortaokulu, Turkey
- Clemens-Brentano-Europaschule, Germany
- Studienseminar GHRF, Germany

The idea: the STEAM-Labs

The MAIN ELEMENT OF INNOVATION of the project is centered on the design, creation and use of the STEAM-Lab space (based on the needs and conditions of each school), where the main actors of the project (students and trainers, but also the family, citizenships, and any social institution) can

find/create/share and work, any type of contents with a focus on developing STEAM competences, for example developing projects related with cultural heritage, using formal, non-formal and informal approaches in an international context.

The STEAM-Lab is a physical/digital place proposal to be hold in the schools of the project, but also, in other schools associated with the project (related or not with the national associations of some partners), and in general in any type of educational activity around the world in the future. These processes should strengthen both, the competences recognition as well as the adaptation of new innovative practices developed in other countries and social environments for a better students' capability.

This approach is focused on the MAIN EXPECTED IMPACT of the project:

- Identification and study of involvement, motivation, usability, satisfaction and user profile's (depending on the different

- variables associated with diversity, specially focused on social and gender-gap) in the co-design, and creation of STEAM-Labs in the schools (first phase),
- and in the development and assessment of pilot educational projects in the STEAM-Lab (second phase), for a reduction of diversity-gap, and improvement of STEAM vocations in the profiles with higher gap (as for example women).

Intellectual Outputs

For achieving our goals, CreaSTEAM project will:

- Mapping initiatives related to promoting STEAM and best practices among children and young people in order to address diversity-gap (mixed method: quantitative research with qualitative evaluation) (IO 1);
- Develop a framework for schools to implement effective activity packages to promote diversity in STEAM in collaboration with the communities and associations of a region (IO 2).

Activities performed

The project, (accepted 01/10/2020, signed 16/11/2020), began with an initial delay of approx. 2 months, to which must be added the uncertain situation and restrictions in the countries of the project partners (Spain, Italy, Turkey and Germany). In this sense, the 1st meeting of the contact persons of each institution was held virtually on 4/12/2020, in order to review the project globally, its schedule and the actions to be undertaken for each partner.

The Kick Off Meeting was an online meeting on 14th, 15th, 18th January, 2021.

In order to reach CreaSTEAM aims, the main actions put in place to pursue the two intellectual outputs in these months (January 2021 - October 2021) were:

O1: Key concepts & strategies for designing and implementing a STEAM-Lab. Introduction and Conceptualization of STEAM-Labs:

- Tool mapping and possible systems to be implemented in the STEAM-Lab, merging the solutions that we can find in FAB-Labs, MEDIA-Labs, and USER-Labs (https://coggle.it/diagram/X-Cy2_YZrx-l8zDJ/t/technology-in-a-steam-lab-star/87aa2de749f590535e3050cd2eb3f71eea7934008b241419a12782b21f23872e)
- Design and training of teachers in two phases. This activity was planned for the schools outside of the project, but involved as associated schools (2 in Germany, 4 in Italy, 3 in Spain and 3 in Turkey), in order to develop STEAM-Labs or any diversity gap through STEAM approaches:
 - 1) May 2021 (14 and 21/5/2021): Training focused on diversity aspects, maker spaces, how to design a collaborative space, what “I have in my school and what I want?”
 - 2) September 2021 (17 and 20/9/2021): Training Pills, selected from the training of May: Electronics, Diversity, Augmented Reality, Photo-Composition, 3D printing, Usability). All videos, presentations, and support documentation have been archived and are available to member schools in Teacher Training Course platform (TTC).

O2: Framework to bridging the Diversity-gap (October 2020–October 2021). Mapping resources, initiatives, systems, etc.:

- 1) Around 100 initiatives were identified (to be completed and formatted in the second year) both in educational approaches and scientific documents.
- 2) Creation of the first version of the Lesson Plan Assessment questionnaire for each practice, exercise and project. Under review by the partners in order to get the final version that we will apply to collect the STEAM-Labs implementations as a way to identify the good practices.
- 3) Creation of the Lesson Plan questionnaire to map all new initiatives:

The image shows a 'CreaSTEAM Unit Plan' form template. It is a purple-bordered document with several white sections for text entry. At the top, there are fields for 'TITLE:', 'DATE:', 'SCHOOL:', 'MAIN TEACHER:', 'AGE LEARNERS:', and 'NUMBER OF TEACHING HOURS:'. Below these is the title 'CreaSTEAM Unit Plan' and a small logo. The form is divided into several sections: 'SUBJECTS INVOLVED:' (with a list of subjects: SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, ARTS), 'IMPLEMENTATION:' (with a list of methods: INQUIRE SKILL, INTERDISCIPLINARY INSTRUCTION, FOSTERS OR CREATIVITY, ADDRESS DIVERSITY GAP, CONSIDERATION / GENDER / ECONOMIC / BELIEFS), 'INSTRUCTION: (ENGINE ONE OR MORE):' (with a list of methods: ACTIVE LEARNING, PROJECT BASED LEARNING, PERSONALIZATION OR LEARNING, SERVICE LEARNING, COLLABORATIVE LEARNING, DESIGN THINKING METHODOLOGIES, INQUIRY BASED LEARNING, TURNING), 'SHORT DESCRIPTION:', 'MATERIALS/RESOURCES:', 'LEARNING OBJECTIVES:', 'LESSON PLAN OUTLINE:', 'RESULTS/EVIDENCES:', and 'PERSONAL NOTES:'. At the bottom, there are logos for TEA, GRETEL, GRIAL, and the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfqQeccLAFSJnCnbQHXPrt87HDVu6z8PHnuHc--cglzWmQJXQ/viewform> .

On October 7th and 8th, 2021, at Gießen, in Germany, the second project transnational meeting was held.

The meeting was attended by all partners. The October 7 session was held at Clemens Brentano Europaschule Meeting, while that of October 8 at Makerspace, both in Gießen.

There have been convivial moments and cultural visits, which have consolidated and strengthened the collaboration and empathy between the partners.

During the meeting, among other issues, the following were discussed:

- Presentation of the schools about how they are developing or thinking about the spaces, the projects and addressing any Diversity Gap of the school or using this concept in their projects to be developed in the STEAM-Lab.
- Presentation on the Evaluation of the STEAMS-Labs. Explanation of the questionnaire, that must be made at the beginning and at the end to evaluate the perception of the students.
- Dissemination strategies and activities. In this sense, even schools have started their own process through news on their websites, promotional videos and presentations within their social sphere, as can be seen for example in the following links, and/or in the recent presentations of the schools (available on Zenodo), with links to these promotional videos. Some examples of sites and external communications:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5595760> .
- Planning of the next transnational project meeting in Italy, in Rome, in February 2022.

Video-summary of the first transnational meeting of the CreaSTEAM Project:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6dsNMOwFbWM>

Next steps

The most important activity that the project will address in this second year of activity is the implementation and dissemination of STEAM-Labs, as they were conceived and planned in the first phase of the project. Until 12 schools will develop a STEAM-Lab using the documentation created by the CreaSTEAM project to develop STEAM spaces in their schools and address any diversity gap.

In the more general perspective of the realization of the project and the expected results, it will proceed in the action of pursuit of:

- the creation of a complete guide and map of resources focused on the different lines of STEAM focused on diversity-gap reduction, to make easier for any type of educational institution the implementation of new proposals;
- and a guide to design, create and develop STEAM projects in a new concept of specific laboratory, the STEAM-Lab, which merge the options and resources of Fab-Lab, Media-Lab and User-Lab spaces.

Official website: <https://creasteam.eu/>

European Commission website : <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplus-project-details/#project/2020-1-ES01-KA201-082601>

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